

Lead(II) and Tin(II) Complexes of Monobasic Bidentate Triazene-1-oxides

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Syntheses and characterisation of lead(II) and tin(IV) complexes of monobasic bidentate triazene-1-oxides (TH) are described. The complexes were characterised by elemental analyses, conductance, molecular weights in freezing benzene and infrared spectral studies. The lead(II) complexes, $[PbT_2]$, are either square planar or ψ -pyramidal while the tin(IV) complexes, $[SnT_2I_2]$, have *trans* di-iodo octahedral structure.

TRIAZENE-1-OXIDES (I) have been used both as analytical reagents^{1,2} and chelating agents for transition metal ions^{3,4}. Recently, we extended the studies of the coordination behaviour of these ligands to zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II)⁵. We report here the preparation and properties of triazene-1-oxide complexes of lead(II) and tin(IV). The ligands are abbreviated as TH and the metal complexes as MT_2 . Positions of the substituents in the aromatic ring are indicated by using prefixes *o*-, *m*- and *p*- with respect to the N-C (Ar) bond.

Experimental

Preparation of the ligand and the metal chelates : All chemicals used were of AnalaR or chemically pure grade. Ligands were synthesized following published procedures^{1,7}. Lead acetate (0.001 mole) was dissolved in 15 ml dehydrated alcohol and added to 20 ml of the alcoholic solution of TH (0.002 mole) saturated with anhydrous sodium acetate. The mixture was warmed for a few min and the heavy crystalline precipitate of the complex was filtered. Tin tetraiodide (0.001 mole) was dissolved in 10 ml alcohol and added to 20 ml of the alcoholic solution of TH (0.002 mole). The crystalline complex of tin(IV) was collected and dried over silica gel in a desiccator.

Analysis of the elements : Lead was estimated as sulphate¹⁸ and tin as tin dioxide¹⁸ after decomposing the complex with 1:1 hydrochloric acid over a water bath. Carbon and hydrogen were determined at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. Nitrogen was estimated by Dumas' method and iodine by Volhard's method¹⁹. For the estimation of iodine the sample was decomposed by boiling with strong caustic soda solution for 1 hr and the resulting solution was used.

Physical measurements : Conductance was measured in nitromethane using a Philips conductance bridge. Molecular weights were determined in freezing benzene using Beckmann's method. IR spectra in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow and in the range 600-20 cm^{-1} at R.S.I.C., Madras.

Results and Discussion

Lead(II) complexes, $[PbT_2]$: Lead(II) acetate reacts with triazene-1-oxides in (1 : 2) molar ratio in alcoholic medium and gives complexes of the general formula $[PbT_2]$. *Bis*(ligand) lead(II) complexes have been characterised by satisfactory elemental analysis (Table 1), non-electrolytic nature ($\Lambda_M \approx 1.0$ ohms⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹) in nitromethane and monomer molecular weights (within 0.5-1.5%) in freezing benzene (Table 2). Repeated attempts to raise the coordination number of lead(II) from four to six by reacting PbT_2 with pyridine, bipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline in acetone yielded no success. The four coordinate nature of *bis*(triazene-1-oxidato)lead(II) has been further supported by ir spectral studies of the ligands and their lead(II) complexes in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} in CsI discs (Table 2). ν_{N-H}^a band of the ligands at ~ 3190 cm^{-1} completely disappears showing replacement of the N-proton by the lead(II) ion. ν_{C-C} (phenyl) at ~ 1600 cm^{-1} is slightly lowered to 1590 cm^{-1} . $\nu_{-N=N-}$ (sym. triazene) giving multiple bands between 1535-1430 cm^{-1} is lowered⁶ to 1505-1375 cm^{-1} . $\nu_{N=O}$ at 1310 cm^{-1} is considerably lowered to 1245 cm^{-1} due to $N \rightarrow O \rightarrow M$ bond formation^{7,8}. The very sharp band at 1245 cm^{-1} also includes a broad band at 1220 cm^{-1} (ν_{C-C} phenyl in plane). ν_{Pb-O} at ~ 455 cm^{-1} and ν_{Pb-N} at ~ 520 cm^{-1} have also been identified. These band assignments are supported by ν_{Hg-O} at ~ 450 cm^{-1} and ν_{Hg-N} at ~ 510 cm^{-1} reported earlier in connection with a series of phenylmercury(II) complexes of triazene-1-oxides⁹⁻¹¹. Attempts were made to react lead(IV) tetraacetate with triazene-1-oxides in alcohol. No crystalline solid product could be obtained.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISATION DATA OF [PbT₂] AND [SnT₂I₂] COMPLEXES

Complex	R	Ar	Colour	m.p. °C	Analysis % ; Found (Calcd.)				
					M	I	N	O	H
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Yellow	146-47	32.73 (32.81)	—	15.40 (15.66)	45.60 (45.64)	2.83 (3.17)
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	„	150-51	31.14 (31.44)	—	12.99 (12.75)	47.20 (47.35)	3.58 (3.69)
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	Green	163-64	29.84 (29.59)	—	12.17 (12.00)	40.92 (41.13)	2.90 (2.57)
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	Deep brown	185	28.61 (28.74)	—	16.15 (15.75)	40.30 (39.95)	2.61 (2.49)
SnT ₂ I ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	Yellow	194-95	16.37 (16.01)	34.65 (34.25)	11.03 (11.32)	22.70 (22.66)	1.95 (1.90)
SnT ₂ I ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	Orange	170-71	17.18 (16.94)	36.21 (36.24)	11.95 (11.99)	27.60 (28.04)	2.72 (2.85)
SnT ₂ I ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	Brown	183	15.04 (14.90)	31.39 (31.88)	10.90 (10.54)	37.95 (37.84)	2.87 (2.91)
SnT ₂ I ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	Yellow	189	13.80 (13.71)	29.46 (29.34)	10.03 (10.16)	33.21 (33.37)	2.01 (2.08)
SnT ₂ I ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	Deep brown	159-60	14.21 (14.40)	30.82 (30.80)	10.42 (10.19)	36.25 (36.15)	2.69 (2.51)

TABLE 2—CONDUCTANCE, MOLECULAR WEIGHTS AND MAJOR IR BANDS OF [PbT₂] AND [SnT₂I₂]

Compound	R	Ar	Molar conductance in nitromethane*	Mol. wt. benzene	IR bands (cm ⁻¹)				
					N-H	N→O	M-O	M-N	Sn-I
TH	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	—	—	3170 s	1305 m	—	—	—
TH	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	—	—	3205 s	1295 m	—	—	—
TH	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	—	—	3150 s	1300 m	—	—	—
TH	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	—	—	3150 s	1300 m	—	—	—
TH	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	—	—	3180 s	1310 m	—	—	—
SnT ₂ I ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	10.0	689.7(700.7)†	—	1250 s	480 m	580 m	186 s
SnT ₂ I ₂	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	14.0	737.2(741.7)	—	1245 s	485 m	575 m	184 s
SnT ₂ I ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	19.0	702.1(696.7)	—	1242 s	480 m	580 m	—
SnT ₂ I ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	17.0	817.4(824.7)	—	1240 s	470 m	580 m	—
SnT ₂ I ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	17.0	902.4(865.7)	—	1240 s	480 m	575 m	—
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	0.0	633.1(631.2)	—	1245 s	460 m	525 m	—
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ CH ₃ (p)	0.7	643.6(649.2)	—	1245 s	455 m	520 m	—
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ Cl(p)	0.4	788.1(800.2)	—	1248 s	455 m	520 m	—
PbT ₂	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ NO ₂ (p)	0.3	Low solubility	—	1240 s	450 m	525 m	—

* ohms⁻¹cm²mole⁻¹; s=strong; m=medium.

† Values within the parentheses are Calcd. ones.

Tin(IV) complexes, [SnT₂I₂]: Tin(IV) iodide reacts with triazene-1-oxides in alcoholic medium in (1 : 3) molar proportion to produce crystalline complexes of the empirical formula [SnT₂I₂] (Table 1). The complexes are non-electrolytes ($\Lambda_M \approx 10$ -19 ohms⁻¹ cm² mole⁻¹) in nitromethane and give monomeric molecular weights (within ~4%) in freezing benzene (Table 2). Several attempts to replace the two iodine atoms by strong field ligands like bipyridyl or *o*-phenanthroline in acetone had no success. This may be taken as an indication of the *trans* configuration of the two iodine atoms in [SnT₂I₂] complexes. The six coordinate nature and the *trans* configuration of the two iodine atoms receive further support from the ir spectral studies in the range 4000-20 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). The ν_{N-H} band at ~3190 cm⁻¹ in the free ligand is absent in the complexes. Besides, the $\nu_{N \rightarrow O}$ band is shifted from 1310 cm⁻¹ to 1245 cm⁻¹. The $\nu_{S_{N-O}}$ band appears at ~480 cm⁻¹ while the $\nu_{S_{N-N}}$ stretch is observed¹² at ~580 cm⁻¹. A single sharp band at ~185 cm⁻¹ unambiguously demonstrates the *trans* disposition of the two coordinated iodide groups, unlike two $\nu_{S_{N-I}}$ stretches observed in the case of a series of *cis*-[Sn(β -diket)₂X₂]

(β -diketH- β -diketone; X=F or I)¹³. Attempts to obtain similar products with SnCl₄ and SnBr₄ ended in failures.

The presence of an inert pair of electrons in lead(II) is expected to influence the stereochemistries of its complexes¹⁴. It, however, remains an unsettled point as to whether lead(II) uses its lone pair to fill up one of the coordination sites in ψ -type geometries or retains its 6s² character giving a planar geometry as in *bis*(benzoylacetato)-lead(II)¹⁵. However, tin(IV) has spherical symmetry and its complexes [SnT₂I₂] acquire a six coordinate *trans* octahedral geometry¹⁶.

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References

1. D. N. PUROHIT, *Talanta*, 1967, 14, 353.
2. D. CHAKRAVORTI and A. K. MAJUMDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1977, 54, 258.

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3. R. L. DUTTA and S. LAHIRY, *Chem. and Ind. (London)*, 1961, 78 and subsequent papers.
4. A. CHAKRAVORTY, B. BEHRA and P. S. ZACHARIAS, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1968, 2, 85 and subsequent papers.
5. R. L. DUTTA and R. SHARMA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1980, 40, 1204.
6. A. D. CROSS and R. A. JONES, "An Introduction to Practical Infrared Spectroscopy", Butterworths, London, 1969.
7. J. V. QUAGLIANO, J. FUJITA, G. FRANZ, J. D. PHILIPS, J. A. WALMSLEY and S. Y. TYRRE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 3770.
8. J. VINCINGUERRA, P. G. SIMPSON, Y. KAKIUTI and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1963, 2, 286.
9. E. P. BERTIN, J. NAKAGOWA, S. MIZUSHIMA, T. J. LANE and J. V. QUAGLIANO, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 525.
10. K. C. MALHOTRA and S. C. CHAUDHURY, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1974, 27, 79.
11. R. L. DUTTA and S. K. SATAPATHI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, 59, 332.
12. Y. KAWASKI, T. TANAKA and R. OKAWARA, *Spectrochim. Acta., A*, 1966, 22, 1571.
13. R. W. JONES, JR. and R. C. FAY, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1973, 12, 2599.
14. L. E. ORGEL, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 3815.
15. P. J. DURRANT and B. DURRANT, "Introduction to Advanced Inorganic Chemistry", Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., 1962, p. 640.
16. C. F. BELL, "Metal Chelation", Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1977, p. 34.
17. M. ELKINS and L. HUNTER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1346.
18. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans Green & Co. Ltd., London, 1961, pp. 504, 482, 267.